

The **CM language** was developed from scratch by the Task Force on Automation and Reproducibility at **MLCommons**, cTuning foundation and cKnowledge in an open and transparent way with public **Discord discussions**, important feedback from **Neural Magic**, **Telecommunications Technology Association**, **One Stop Systems**, **Nutanix**, **Collabora**, **Deelvin Solutions Inc.** , **HiPEAC** , **OctoAI**, **AMD** and **NVIDIA**, and contributions from **academia and industry**.

CM helps to implement modular, portable and technology-agnostic benchmarks with a common interface while reducing all development, benchmarking and optimization costs. For example, CM automation for MLPerf benchmarks makes it possible to automatically plug in different ML models (including support for **SparseZoo** from Neural Magic, Model Hub from **Hugging Face** and BERT pruners from the **NeurIPS** paper), data sets (Hugging Face, **Papers with Code**, **Kaggle**) and all major AI frameworks while automatically adapting to rapidly evolving software/hardware stacks (including support for Nvidia, Intel, AMD, Qualcomm, Arm-based systems and any other new hardware).

Here is a highlight of new features available to everyone in the latest release:

- We improved **MLCommons CK playground** with a better visualization and comparison of inference results via our **beta MLPerf explorer**.
 - It is now possible to generate comparison reports before, during or after submission as demonstrated at <https://github.com/mlcommons/ck/tree/master/cm-mlops/report/mlperf-inference-v3.1-analysis-ctuning> :
1. For the first time, all reference implementations were benchmarked in the edge category closed division in v3.1 using CM.
 2. The community obtained competitive performance results using Nvidia implementation with CM automation on AWS and GCP.
 3. CM helped several external companies including One Stop Systems submit top performance numbers on an Nvidia-powered Rigel Edge Supercomputer.

4. We benchmarked a small 4-core Azure instance with Intel's BERT implementation automated by CM.
5. We added a new CM feature to automate and visualize multiple experiments such exploring sparsity, quantization and batch size of BERT models across multiple AMD, Intel and ARM-based systems in terms of performance, accuracy and power consumption.

Performance per accelerator for bert-99 Offline scenario in closed division edge category

Accuracy vs Performance

- It is possible to use a common CM interface to run all MLPerf inference benchmarks natively or inside containers and prepare open and closed submissions with compliance tests in an automated and reproducible way with practically any combination of
 1. all MLPerf models including GPT-J with preliminary support for DeepSparse Zoo, Hugging Face Hub and BERT pruners from the NeurIPS paper
 2. Main MLPerf implementations including all reference, Nvidia, Intel, TFLite, Modular Inference Library;

3. Main frameworks and run-times including DeepSparse, PyTorch, TensorFlow, TFLite, TVM, TensorRT, ONNX, NCNN, Triton; we plan to add support for QAIC and other frameworks for v4.0
- Diverse hardware including Coral TPU, Nvidia GPUs (A100,T4,L4,RTX 4090, Jetson Orin), Intel/AMD servers, Graviton, NeoVerse, Apple metal

We are also excited to see that our CM automation language is now used outside MLCommons:

- The community validated CM at the ACM/IEEE MICRO'23 conference to provide a unified interface to prepare, run, reproduce and visualize results from different papers: <https://github.com/ctuning/cm-reproduce-research-projects/tree/main/script>
- We were appointed as MLPerf liaisons for the Student Cluster Competition at SuperComputing'23 to help students and researchers run and optimize MLPerf inference benchmarks across different servers on the spot using CM automation.
- We will give a CM-MLPerf tutorial at the IEEE IISWC'23 on October 1st: <https://iiswc.org/iiswc2023/#/program/> - please feel free to join us there.

We would like to deeply thank many individuals who helped us develop, test or discuss this open-source automation technology including [Anandhu S](#), [Michael Goin](#), [jose hernandez](#), [Ilya Kozulin](#), [Amrutha Sheleenderan](#), [Aditya Kumar Shaw](#), Justin Faust, [Datta Nimmaturi](#), [Byoungjun Seo](#), [Nandeeka Nayak](#), [Resmi Arjun](#), Nijo Jacob, Stanley Mwangi, [Chloé Tessier](#), [Iliya Slavutin](#), [Miroslav Hodak](#), [Mitchelle Rasquinha](#), [Victor Bittorf](#), [Rakshith Vasudev](#), [Sachin Idgunji](#), [Arun Tejusve Raghunath Rajan](#), [Kenneth Leach](#), [Ramesh Chukka](#), [Nitin Vairagare](#), [Ashwin Nanjappa](#), [Ethan Cheng](#), Warren Schultz, [Fabrice Costa](#), [Kasper Mecklenburg](#), [James Goel](#), P.Eng., [Omar Benjelloun](#), [Carlos Maltzahn](#), [Thierry Moreau](#), [David Tafur](#), [Pablo Gonzalez Mesa](#), [Alexandros Karagyris](#), Nathan Wasson, [Vijay Janapa Reddi](#), [David Kanter](#) and [Peter Mattson](#). Special thanks to [One Stop Systems](#) for

showcasing the 1st MLPerf inference results on Rigel Edge Supercomputer, and to [Telecommunications Technology Association](#) for sharing their platforms with us to add CM automation for DLRMv2 available to everyone.

We continue enhancing the MLCommons CM/CK technology to help everyone automatically select or co-design the most efficient end-to-end AI solutions based on their requirements and constraints. We welcome everyone to join our [public Discord server](#) if you are interested to benchmark and showcase your platforms, models, software and hardware in the next MLPerf inference v4.0 submission round and/or use our unified CM interface to implement modular benchmarks and share, reproduce and reuse research projects!

Looking forward to collaborating with you,

[Grigori Fursin](#) and [Arjun Suresh](#)

MLCommons Task Force on Automation and Reproducibility, the cTuning foundation and [cKnowledge.org](#)

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